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Relations between educators and preschoolers, in the context of aggression and conflicts

Abstract: *The article brings to the fore the role of the educator in mediating and resolving conflicts in preschool educational institutions. In kindergarten, most conflicts appear as a result of aggressive behaviors, therefore the environmental factors that can favor the appearance of aggression, as well as*

the relationship between the educator and the child, are presented. The article presents the results of research on bidirectional links between the quality of teacher-child relationships and children's interest and pre-academic skills in literacy and math in Finland. The article also offers examples of educators' intervention in resolving conflicts between preschoolers.

Keywords: *aggression, conflicts, preschoolers, educators.*

Rezumat: *Articolul aduce în prim-plan rolul educatorului în medierea și soluționarea conflictelor în instituțiile de învățământ preșcolar. La grădiniță cele mai multe conflicte apar ca urmare a comportamentelor agresive, de aceea sunt prezentați factorii de mediu care pot favoriza apariția agresiunii, precum și relațiile dintre educator și copil. Se prezintă rezultatele cercetărilor despre legăturile bidirecționale dintre calitatea relațiilor profesor-copil și interesul copiilor și abilitățile pre-academice în alfabetizare și matematică în Finlanda. Se oferă exemple de intervenții ale educatorilor în rezolvarea conflictelor dintre preșcolari.*

Cuvinte-cheie: *agresivitate, conflicte, preșcolari, educatori.*

Aggressiveness, in a broad sense, may be understood as an integral part of an entity, 'thanks to which the living being can obtain the satisfaction of its vital needs' [6]. Aggression is associated, by several specialists, with the intention to produce violent acts that have as repercussions the injury of other people or some destruction. While not all aggressive manifestations are carried out with the intention of doing harm, in many situations aggression has an impulsive or instinctual expression that does not directly involve conscious control. Mihai Epuran and his colleagues notice aggressive manifestations from the age of one year, when 'the child breaks the toy, tears the pages of the books, pulls out the eyes of the dolls' [3, p.195]. Most likely, these aggressive manifestations could have an important exploratory role on the environment, especially since this kind of reaction can also be observed at the first meetings between peers. Children are tempted, from the very first meetings, to establish physical contact, which is achieved especially through chasing games. During the game, these children push each other, throw each other, and sometimes they can hit each other. Such behavior resembles a real fight, but these manifestations do not degenerate into violence. However, most often they will result in resentment, crying and breaking of contact. In the preschool environment, most conflicts arise as a result of aggressive behavior. The teaching staff has an essential role of mediator and facilitator of conflict resolution,

given that they start from faulty communication. Some preschoolers fail to express themselves or do not do it adequately, others are introverted and do not socialize, so they find a way to express themselves through aggression. All these behaviors must be corrected in order to achieve a warm atmosphere, conducive to learning.

The relationships between the educator and preschoolers are generally polarized into feelings of sympathy, mutual trust or, on the contrary, antipathy, mistrust and even hostility. There are also cases when the spiritual contact between teacher and student does not pass the zone of indifference: the class does not exist for the teacher and neither does the teacher for the class. The initiative must belong to the teacher, who, taking into account the essential law of interpersonal affective relations, according to which sympathy and goodwill beget sympathy and goodwill, while antipathy and hostility arouse feelings of the same quality, must lead, direct these relations, and structure them on collaboration. Research has found that some teachers do not react adequately to students' answers, either correct or wrong.

Indifference to the student's personality threatens his basic spiritual needs, self-respect, the need for emotional response from those around him, the need for long-term security and success, as well as the need to belong to a group and to be accepted by it. Traditional school practice left us with the image of a teacher who wants

to dominate the students and subordinate them. In such a climate, nothing is done out of conviction and passion. It is necessary to make the transition from the old type of relationships to relationships in which the teacher collaborates with the students. His main activity will not be teaching, but engaging students in investigations and independent work. Relationships based on esteem and mutual respect also require appropriate language. Ironic and offensive expressions disturb the students' attitude towards their teacher and make it difficult to create a favorable climate for creative work in the classroom.

The results obtained from research highlight the fact that the more forms of punishment (irony, insult, ridicule) are used, the less their effect. The teacher who knows the value of positive appreciation will not shy away from a slight overestimation of the student's performance: he will appreciate the student more than he deserves, in order to make him fully deserve the appreciation, to rise to the level of the appreciation made. Experience shows us that a teacher with good results improves his relations with weak students by giving them enough positive appreciation. Even faced with minor school achievements, the teacher who knows the value of positive appreciation uses it, trying to permanently develop the students' confidence in their own strengths.

By not paying more attention to the way of distributing the forms of reinforcement, the balance of punishments and rewards, of positive and negative appreciation, it is possible to depreciate the student's personality, when scolding is used excessively, and above all, when scolding does not retain a limited character, but takes the form of a global depreciation. It is no coincidence that teachers who encourage students more through praise achieve better results in the education process. They appreciate "difficult students" positively even for some minor progress, trying in this way to permanently develop the students' confidence [7, p. 44].

In the education system, it is the teacher who plays a key role, because education is to a large extent what the state-led educational policy wants. The teaching profession is assigned functions, covering specific tasks. There are many classifications of teaching functions, but the best known is the one dividing them into teaching, educational, caring, environmental, research, and life orientation of young people activities [10].

The age of preschool children (3 to 6 years old) is associated with intensified activities related to the care and educational and didactic functions of teachers. They focus on tasks related to: creating a safe, friendly atmosphere for children, taking into account their developmental needs (caring function); planning and organizing educational activities, developing children's social competences and cooperation in the peer group and with adults (educational function); coordinating cognitive

processes that develop the competences of preschoolers in terms of knowledge and practical skills, primarily preparing them to start learning at school.

All activities related to the implementation of tasks resulting from the performed professional functions are based on educational interactions that have been properly selected and adapted to the psychophysical abilities of children. The factors determining the quality of a teacher's work can be divided into:

- conditions of psychological nature – related to functional motivational mechanisms for the implementation of goals and tasks resulting from professional functions and general personality competences, such as ambition, creativity, openness, or understanding the need for continuous development;
- pedagogical conditions, resulting from clearly defined goals and educational tasks, as well as appropriate preparation for the profession;
- praxeological conditions, related to an efficient planning of educational activities, as well as monitoring the quality of one's own work;
- conditions of social nature, relating to interpersonal relations in the institution, the organizational climate, the social prestige of the teacher's profession and the social and professional roles he performs, as well as the appropriate material and organizational prosperity of the workplace [10].

The relationship between teacher and student does not only have an intellectual side. The affective factor has a special importance on the student's intellectual performance. Creating a good mood in the classroom is a necessary condition for avoiding school failure. Each lesson takes place in a particular affective climate, and the mood of the class varies depending on the teacher's.

Knowing and understanding the child is a sine qua non condition of his education. Mihai Ralea draws attention to the fact that interpersonal relationships are created in conditions of intimacy or familiarity. Intimacy should not be confused with familiarity. The former is the expression of a respectful communion, the latter – a desecration. Similar situations can also occur in the context of the educator-educated relationship, of a sustained educational activity, a factor of its progress, as long as the former creates and maintains a certain balance, that psychostasis indispensable for any success (sensory, affective, volitional). Intimacy, therefore, creates and increases the educator-educated, educated-educator trust, favoring their mutual knowledge.

In the kindergarten, the role of the educator naturally falls to the teacher and the role of the educated is taken over by the preschooler. The education process aims at the multi-lateral development of the child's skills – not at the sacrifice of originality, of the specific beauty of the personality. The development of skills involves their early comprehension and cultivation. On the other hand, experience shows that

the results of pedagogical actions and measures depend a lot on the individual characteristics of the children.

The need for a psychological knowledge of children is thus felt at every step in the process of their education; the same educational measures and procedures can yield special results, sometimes opposite, depending on the particularities of the children to whom they are applied.

Punishments are an eloquent example. For some children a harsher admonition may be enough, even for a serious misdeed, while in other cases a severe punishment must be applied even for an insignificant mistake. Also, in the matter of requirements, individual particularities must be taken into account; to spoiled and capricious children we must present requirements in a categorical form; to stubborn, impulsive children, who do not know how to control themselves, we may give tasks without insisting on their immediate fulfillment.

Therefore, the application of pedagogical methods and procedures, as well as the establishment of requirements, involve a knowledge of the individual characteristics of children. We know the child by educating him and we educate him better by knowing him. Knowing and educating the child are two very closely intertwined activities in the kindergarten. By observing the child during preschool activities the educators strive to discover his positive character traits, develop them and, by relying on them, prevent and eliminate negative traits.

In addition to professional training, the educator must learn the general principles and laws of development of nature and society. An important condition for becoming a good educator is to have firm knowledge and convictions. Only a well-educated educator can educate in turn. The educator-child relationship must be a friendly relationship. The child must trust the educator, come to him with an open heart, say openly anything he wants and thinks. In turn, the educator must receive him and respond to him with the same sincerity, with the same trust. In order for this to be done correctly, the educator ought to have complete training. Will we educators be able to answer the “whys” of the children if we don’t know the real answer? Do we have the right to give children the wrong answers? Certainly not! So at any moment, in any activity, we must be prepared to answer the children calmly, patiently, but above all clearly and correctly. In the activities carried out in kindergarten and outside it, any idea conveyed to the children must be explained in their own way, especially when they show interest and start asking questions. The educator’s love for children, the pleasure and joy of working with children are embodied in his way of behaving towards children, of knowing how to approach them, of answering their spontaneous questions, of coming down to their level of understanding – in a word, in being their friend.

The educator, having a high moral level, should act with a sense of responsibility and professional competence

in structuring the educator-child relationship, so that the child, from object of education, becomes more and more the subject of his own education. Children ought to be taught to observe, to ask, to search, to research, and to work.

There are environmental factors that can favor aggression, increasing the risk of disruptive behavior: a low socioeconomic and educational level of the family, affective deficiencies, an overly authoritarian parental educational style or, on the opposite pole, exaggerated permissiveness, unclear rules, strained family relationships, with violent conflicts between family members, caused by excessive alcohol consumption, mental illness etc. For this reason, one of the concerns of educational institutions is to prevent violence and aggressive behavior in children [2, p. 57].

H. Montagner observed in children who do not rest enough sudden bouts of aggression, followed by moments of absolute isolation. Aggression in children is most often due to a deep dissatisfaction, consequent to a lack of affection or to a feeling of personal devaluation. When, for example, despite his best efforts, a child is punished because he does not meet the demands of his parents, they apply an extremely unfair treatment, which can lead to his rebellion or collapse [apud 6, p.19].

T. Rudică underlines the fact that some deviant behaviors can be generated by the educational differences between the adult members of the family. The family environment is not strictly limited to the members of the family group, but may also include other adults. In some cases these people can play an important role in influencing the nature of the child’s relationship with the parents. According to A. Berge, “what complicates family pedagogy is the number of jurisdictions to which the child must submit. There are families in which the smallest measure of educational order arouses the cries of indignation of grandparents, uncles, aunts, friends, etc., who present their opinions, contradict each other, criticize severity or indulgence, suggest saving systems and solutions. Small children are great craftsmen when it comes to taking advantage of these divergences to free themselves from any rule”. Most of the time, however, grandparents are a source of rich and precious experiences for the child. Thus, for children from a large family, grandparents provide an “extra home”, which complements and completes the family environment itself and in which each of the children enjoys equal attention. A jealous child, who believes that another child (brother or sister) has taken his place in the heart of his parents, comes to his grandparents, where he finds a place of refuge. It is true, however, that sometimes grandparents are particularly protective and indulgent with their grandchildren, protecting and defending them from their parents’ punishments even when they shouldn’t. Of course, such direct interventions in the attributions of the parents shakes their authority, changes the position of the child towards the parents, disrupts family relations, giving rise to tensions and conflicts, as a result of

which the child is the one to suffer. Likewise, excessively indulgent grandparents, who allow the child to express himself unchecked, raise grandchildren who are naughty and over-pampered [5, p.112].

Parents must prove a sense of measure in their attitude and demands towards the child, doubled by the ability to foresee the reactions and internal states of the child. The exaggerated demands shown by some parents towards their children favor school failures and cause “intellectual intoxication”, generating irritability and even aggression in relation to school tasks. According to A. Berge, the child’s defects are nothing but the visible part of a deep conflict between parent and child: “A defect is not an essential imperfection of the being, but a special and aberrant way of acting to the demands of the external world. The defect manifests a difficulty in adaptation; a difficult child is almost always a child who has certain difficulties” [5, p. 113].

Researchers from the University of Jyväskylä, the University of Eastern Finland, and the New York University of Abu Dhabi investigated bidirectional links between the quality of teacher–child relationships and children’s interest and pre-academic skills in literacy and math in Finland. Participants were 461 Finnish kindergarteners (6-year-olds) and their teachers (48). The study is part of the Teacher Stress Study, led by Professor Marja-Kristiina Lerkkanen and Associate Professor Eija Pakarinen at the University of Jyväskylä. The results indicated that teacher-perceived conflict predicted lower interest and pre-academic skills in both literacy and math.

It is possible that when children experience conflict with teachers, the negative emotions attached to these conflicts are harmful for children’s engagement in learning and diminish their interest in academic tasks. It is also possible that children experiencing conflicts are missing out on time on learning literacy and math, either because they are disengaged from instructional activities or because teachers have to spend more instructional time on behavioral management. The findings highlight the importance of kindergarten teachers being aware of how their relationships with children can influence children’s later schooling. It would be important to develop pre-service and in-service programs and interventions to assist teachers in building supportive, low conflict relationships with children. Teacher education programs may also benefit from educating teachers not only about academic content and pedagogical practices but also in strategies that build supportive relationships with children [11].

Teachers pay different levels of attention to conflicts between preschoolers. They also have different ways to intervene in the conflict. Certain studies have made a more detailed classification of teachers’ intervention and the nature of intervention methods.

E. Betsy states that there are two ways of resolving conflicts among preschoolers: the authoritarian and the

evasive way [2]. S. Jenkins et al. did another classification: avoidance, compulsion, and cooperation. Educators who adopt avoidance strategies think they will completely avoid intervention if children are at peace with their actions in conflict. Educators who adopt coercive strategies argue that such strategies can produce results quickly. However, they deny children the chance to learn to resolve conflicts. By using coercive strategies, teachers use authority and continuous control to separate the conflicting parties. And they don’t allow the children to be actively involved in the process. The cooperative strategy gives the teacher the role of mediator [3]. Zhao Kai points out that there are four types of teachers’ responses in the context of conflicts between preschoolers: inspiration, guidance, information, and demonstration in decision-making and superficial control.

Conclusions: The ability to resolve conflicts has a major importance in the social development of preschoolers. Teacher intervention can effectively improve the level of conflict resolution between children. Researchers have conducted a number of studies on peer conflicts, types of conflict resolution strategies, factors affecting conflict, and solution strategies. In conclusion, the educator has an essential role not only in delivering teaching and promoting learning, but also in guiding preschoolers towards non-aggressive behaviors and mediating, solving conflicts that arise between preschoolers.

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